

Model-based investigation of distributed sensing in dielectric elastomer membranes

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ABSTRACT

When a dielectric elastomer (DE) membrane is used as a deformation sensor, changes in its electrical capacitance can be exploited to reconstruct the transducer average strain. At sufficiently high frequencies, however, a DE behaves more like an RC transmission line than just a capacitor. By detecting changes in the frequency response of the resulting DE transmission line, one can implement advanced sensing paradigms in which single-port measurements of the impedance allow estimating a distributed deformation pattern along the membrane. In this work, we present a parametric study aimed at evaluating how material properties, geometry, and deformation patterns influence a DE membrane's impedance frequency response, which in turns provides a measure of the membrane's ability to work as a distributed sensor. The analysis relies on a previously validated physics-based continuum model, used to estimate the impedance frequency response at the input port of a deformed DE membrane. Parametric studies show that the ability of the system to resolve deformation patterns (i.e., generating different impedance profiles) strongly depends on some specific parameters, such as the dependence of the electrode sheet resistance on the stretch. The results provide useful insights on the material requirements for the dielectric and electrode materials, and the limits in terms of measurable deformation profiles.

Keywords: Dielectric Elastomer, Electrodes modelling, Electrical Impedance, Distributed sensing

1. INTRODUCTION

A dielectric elastomer (DE) transducer consists in a deformable capacitor made of a highly stretchable dielectric (e.g., silicone, acrylic) coated by compliant electrodes (e.g., carbon-based). Other than offering possible applications as actuators¹ and generators,² DEs can be also used as sensors.³ A DE sensor is capable of converting an externally applied strain,⁴ force,⁵ or pressure⁶ into measurable changes of their electrical properties (e.g., impedance). Applications areas for DE sensors include automotive, human motion tracking, intelligent wearables, and human machine interfaces.³

In almost all applications, the electrical parameter which is used to reconstruct the DE mechanical state is the capacitance,^{7–10} as this generally results in high accuracy. It is remarked that DEs can be used as piezoresistive sensors as well, leveraging the changes of the resistance of their electrodes upon stretching.¹¹ Despite being simpler in terms of reading electronics, this approach is expected to lead to less accurate results than the capacitive one due to nonlinearities, and thus is generally less popular in the literature. Approximating the DE electrical impedance as a simple lumped capacitor, however, is only valid within frequencies up to few hundred Hz. When the frequency increases at sufficiently high values, a DE behaves as a RC transmission line due to the presence of the spatially-distributed compliant electrodes with finite conductivity.¹² In principle, by detecting changes in the profile of the DE electrical impedance within a given frequency range (in which both resistive and capacitive effects are relevant), and processing the retrieved information with suitable data analysis tools, more information on the membrane state can be extracted. This opens up the possibility of implementing distributed sensing paradigms in DE membranes. For instance, one could determine whether the DE has been stretched in its entirety or only locally, and eventually reconstruct the location of the deformation on the membrane, based

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only on a single-port impedance measurement. This way, the design of the underlying electronics can be greatly simplified.

The first successful implementations of such concept were proposed by Anderson’s group.^{12–14} In these works, the authors developed a DE sensor strip in which the location of an externally applied deformation is detected via a single measurement channel. The distributed sensing task is achieved by treating the DE strip as an RC transmission line, and implementing multi-frequency techniques to measure different points of the frequency response and, in turn, estimate the location of the capacitive change. By combining this principle with machine learning techniques,¹⁵ higher sensing accuracy and contact pressure amplitude detection can eventually be achieved. Although showing remarkable results, those papers solely investigated the method for a predefined DE strip with a relatively simple 1D geometry. To the best of the authors’ knowledge, no studies exist to date which expand this concept to more advanced distributed sensing paradigms which go beyond location/pressure detection in 1D, or which aim at optimizing the layout of a DE sensor (e.g., electrode pattern, material) to maximize the sensitivity for a given task. The latter task, in particular, requires the availability of continuum models which describe how various material and geometry parameters affect the relationship between the imposed deformation pattern and the resulting DE electrical impedance/admittance.

In this work, we present a model-based investigation of distributed sensing effects in a DE strip. Expanding our recent results,¹⁶ we first present a physics-based continuum model which describes the spatial-temporal voltage distribution in a one-dimensional DE strip. The model is based on a partial differential equation that accounts for the capacitance and resistance distribution along the membrane, as well as how those depend on the applied strain field, electrode material (i.e., resistivity), and geometry (i.e., electrode width, thickness, and pattern). Based on this distributed model, a mathematical characterization of the DE equivalent admittance at the input measurement port is derived. All models are formulated in dimensionless form, to maximise generality of the results. A simulation campaign is then conducted to show how admittance changes in the presence of different deformation profiles, and how this change is affected by the electrode material properties or the presence of any external lumped resistive effect. The obtained results provide insights regarding the possibility to tune the DE sensor design with the goal of optimizing its sensing capability and, in turn, increase the accuracy of potential distributed sensing paradigms.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. The working principle of the distributed DE sensing concept is first discussed in Section 2. A dimensionless model of the sensor strip is then derived in Section 3, and used to conduct extensive simulation studies in Section 4. Finally, Section 5 provides concluding remarks and outlines possible future research directions.

2. LAYOUT AND WORKING PRINCIPLE

We hereby make reference to a simple DE sensor geometry, consisting in a planar strip with fixed edges, holding a semi-resistive pair of electrodes (Fig. 1). The strip is made of incompressible material and is subject to a constant stretch in one of the planar directions (y in Fig. 1 left), and a stretch distribution in the other planar direction (x in the figure). The strip is electrically fed through two connections located on a same edge of the device (at $x = 0$), which consist in ideal conductive tracks spanning the strip width. Those connections form the electrical input port through which electrical impedance (or other electrical quantities) can be measured. The system can be regarded as a prototypical sensor used to measure deformations induced by external pressure distributions applied perpendicularly to the surface, such as user’s touches in the DE keyboard proposed by Xu et al.¹²

From an electrical viewpoint, the DE strip is equivalent to an RC transmission line (Fig. 1 right) whose parameters (local resistances and capacitances) vary as a function of the externally applied stretch. As suggested by Anderson et al.,^{13,14} when a harmonic voltage difference is applied on the input tracks, nodes of the transmission line lying on opposite sides of the electrodes with progressively increasing distance from the input port will be subject to harmonic voltage differences with progressively decreasing amplitude (and increasing phase) with respect to the excitation signal because of the presence of distributed resistances. The amplitude of low frequency input signals will remain unaltered throughout the nodes of the strip, whereas the amplitude of high frequency signals will practically fall to zero within a finite distance from the input node, causing such high

frequency signals to reach a finite penetration depth into the network.

Introducing a localized deformation pattern will affect the distribution of voltage waveforms whose penetration depth is longer than the distance between input port and stretch application point, and leave the voltage distributions caused by higher frequency signals unaffected. Dually, the impedance (or admittance) measured at the input port at a given frequency will be affected by deformations applied at any distance lower than the penetration depth.

Leveraging this observation, previous studies¹²⁻¹⁴ suggested that localised deformations might be detected by measuring variations in the spectrum of impedance (which however might be incompatible with real-time applications) or, more practically, by measuring impedance variations at a finite number of pre-selected target frequencies.

Figure 1. De sensor strip: layout and reference frame definition (left); equivalent discretised RC network model (right).

3. MODELLING FRAMEWORK

This section presents a mathematical model suitable to studying distributed sensing effects in DE strips. First, a distributed-parameter model is provided to describe the voltage distribution within a deformed DE strip in both time and frequency domains. The model is then used to derive an expression of the equivalent input-port behavior of the strip, which will be used for subsequent simulation studies. All models are derived in a dimensional form and then normalized to make subsequent simulation studies as generic as possible.

3.1 Distributed electrical model

We model the electrical behaviour of the strip by resorting to a continuum formulation proposed and experimentally validated in our previous work.¹⁶ Given the system symmetry and boundary conditions, the voltage on the electrodes can be assumed uniform along y and be a function of x only. As suggested by Vignotto et al.,¹⁶ due to symmetry the analysis of the system can be restricted to one half of the geometry, by considering one half of the dielectric layer thickness and one resistive electrode, and treating the symmetry plane in between the electrodes as an isopotential surface with potential equal to 0.

Denoting s the curvilinear abscissa on the profile of the deformed strip (Fig. 1 left), and assuming that, in the most general case, an in-series lumped resistor R_s (equally split between positive and negative electrode) is present in between the voltage source and the DE, the voltage distribution $v(s, t)$ on the positive electrode (function of s and the time t) is given by the following partial differential equation and boundary conditions, holding the typical form of diffusion problems:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial v}{\partial t} = \frac{t_d(s)}{2\varepsilon} \frac{\partial}{\partial s} \left(\frac{1}{R_s(s)} \frac{\partial v}{\partial s} \right) \\ v(0, t) - \frac{R_s w}{2R_e(s)} \frac{\partial v(0, t)}{\partial s} = \frac{v_e(t)}{2} \\ \frac{\partial v(l_s, t)}{\partial s} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where l_s is the length of the deformed strip, w is the strip width in the y direction, ε is the DE permittivity (assumed constant), t_d is the total dielectric thickness (the factor 2 at the denominator of the right hand terms

owes to the fact that only 1/2 of the geometry is considered), R_e is the electrode sheet resistance, $v_e(t)$ is the externally applied voltage difference at the input port (with factors 2 resulting from accounting 1/2 of the geometry).

The second boundary condition accounts for the fact that no current flows in/out of the free far edge: this maps into a Neumann condition since the current i flowing through the electrode reads as

$$i = -\frac{w}{R_e(s)} \frac{\partial v}{\partial s}, \quad (2)$$

The first boundary condition accounts for the externally applied voltage and the lumped in-series resistance via Kirchoff's voltage law: $0.5v_e(t) - 0.5R_s i(0, t) - v(0, t) = 0$, leading to a mixed boundary condition, which simplifies to a Dirichlet condition ($v(0, t) = 0.5v_e(t)$) if $R_s = 0$.

Quantities R_e and t_d are assumed to vary with s as a result of locally applied strains. Denoting $\lambda_1(s)$ the distribution of stretch in x direction, the following dependencies can be assumed:

$$t_d(s) = \frac{t_{d0}}{\lambda_1(s)}, \quad R_e(s) = R_{e0} \lambda_1^n(s) \quad (3)$$

where t_{d0} and R_{e0} are the membrane thickness and sheet resistance in the flat mounting configuration, and n is a coefficient characterising the piezoresistive behavior of the electrode via a generic power law¹⁷ If the electrode follows a purely ohmic behavior and its thickness decreases linearly with λ_1 (similar to t_d), then $n = 1$. In contrast to that, in the case in which the sheet resistance is not affected by strains (e.g., because the current flows only on a portion of the electrode thickness, being unaffected by variations in the total electrode thickness), we have $n = 0$.

It is possible to re-parametrise the equations in terms of the position x of material points on the unstretched strip by noting that, by definition

$$\lambda_1(x) = \frac{ds}{dx}. \quad (4)$$

Using Eqs. (4) and (3) within Eq. (1) leads the following partial differential equation:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial v}{\partial t} = \frac{t_{d0}}{2\varepsilon R_{e0} \lambda_1^2(x)} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_1^{n+1}(x)} \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \right) \\ v(0, t) - \frac{R_s w}{2R_e(x)} \frac{\partial v(0, t)}{\partial x} = \frac{v_e(t)}{2} \\ \frac{\partial v(l, t)}{\partial x} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where l is initial (undeformed) length of the strip, and the current is given by

$$i = -\frac{w}{R_{e0} \lambda_1^{n+1}(x)} \frac{\partial v}{\partial x}. \quad (6)$$

In the case of harmonic excitation with amplitude V_0 and angular frequency ω , i.e., $v_e(t) = V_0 \cos(\omega t)$, the steady-state solution to partial differential equation (5) can be obtained by using a phasor description. Indicating $V_\omega \in \mathbb{C}$ a phasor such that $v(x, t) = \Re\{V_\omega(x) \exp(j\omega t)\}$, system (5) simplifies to the following one-dimensional boundary value problem:

$$\begin{cases} j\omega \lambda_1^2(x) V_\omega(x) = \frac{t_{d0}}{2\varepsilon R_{e0}} \frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_1^{n+1}(x)} \frac{dV_\omega}{dx} \right) \\ V_\omega(0) - \frac{R_s w}{2R_{e0} \lambda_1^{n+1}} \frac{dV_\omega(0, t)}{dx} = \frac{V_0}{2} \\ \frac{dV_\omega(l)}{dx} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

We recast the model in a dimensionless form, by introducing the following set of dimensionless variables:

$$x^* = \frac{x}{l}, \quad \omega^* = \frac{2\varepsilon R_{e0} l^2}{t_{d0}} \omega, \quad V_\omega^* = \frac{2}{V_0} V_\omega, \quad I_\omega^* = \frac{2R_{e0} l}{wV_0} I_\omega, \quad R_s^* = \frac{w}{2R_{e0} l} R_s, \quad (8)$$

where I_ω is the current phasor, such that $i(x, t) = \Re\{I_\omega(x) \exp(j\omega t)\}$. Boundary value problem (7) can be thus recast in a dimensionless manner as follows:

$$\begin{cases} j\omega^* \lambda_1^2(x^*) V_\omega^*(x^*) = \frac{d}{dx^*} \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_1^{n+1}(x^*)} \frac{dV_\omega^*}{dx^*} \right) \\ V_\omega^*(0) - \frac{R_s^*}{\lambda_1^{n+1}} \frac{dV_\omega^*(0)}{dx^*} = 1 \\ \frac{dV_\omega^*(1)}{dx^*} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

In the case of undeformed strip ($\lambda_1 = 1$) with ideal connection to the supply voltage ($R_s^* = 0$), Eq. (9) can be solved analytically, leading to the following expressions for the voltage and current phasors distributions:

$$\begin{aligned} V_\omega^*(x^*) &= \frac{\exp\left(\sqrt{\frac{\omega^*}{2}}(1+j)x^*\right)}{1 + \exp(\sqrt{2\omega^*}(1+j))} + \frac{\exp\left(-\sqrt{\frac{\omega^*}{2}}(1+j)x^*\right)}{1 + \exp(-\sqrt{2\omega^*}(1+j))} \\ I_\omega^*(x^*) &= -(1+j)\sqrt{\frac{\omega^*}{2}} \left[\frac{\exp\left(\sqrt{\frac{\omega^*}{2}}(1+j)x^*\right)}{1 + \exp(\sqrt{2\omega^*}(1+j))} - \frac{\exp\left(-\sqrt{\frac{\omega^*}{2}}(1+j)x^*\right)}{1 + \exp(-\sqrt{2\omega^*}(1+j))} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

In the presence of a generic stretch profile $\lambda_1(x)$, boundary value problem (9) can be tackled numerically.

3.2 Equivalent electrical port model

The general model from Section 3.1 will be used here to derive an equivalent input port model of the strip. This is an essential step towards applications, as one would normally measure the global strip behavior via localized measurements of voltage and current at the input electrical port, rather than via electrical sensors distributed along the strip. Solving (7) and calculating the both voltage and current phasors at $x = 0$ allows calculating the system input impedance $Z(\omega) : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ as follows

$$Z(\omega) = \frac{2V_\omega(0)}{I_\omega(0)}, \quad \text{with } I_\omega(x) = -\frac{w}{R_{e0}\lambda_1^{n+1}(x)} \frac{dV_\omega(x)}{dx}, \quad (11)$$

or, dually, the input admittance $Y(\omega) : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ defined as

$$Y(\omega) = \frac{1}{Z(\omega)} = \frac{I_\omega(0)}{2V_\omega(0)}, \quad (12)$$

where the factor 2 accounts for the total voltage drop between the two electrodes (while v and V_ω represent voltage drops between each of the electrodes and the symmetry plane, as in Fig. 1).

Considering the real and imaginary components of complex-valued function Z allows us to express the strip as an equivalent RC series impedance, whose resistive and capacitive components correspond to the electrical parameters that would be measured at the input port using an impedance analyser. Specifically, we can write

$$Z(\omega) = R(\omega) - \frac{j}{\omega C(\omega)} \quad (13)$$

where $R(\omega) : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $C(\omega) : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are given by

$$R(\omega) = \Re \{Z(\omega)\}, \quad C(\omega) = -\frac{1}{\omega \Im \{Z(\omega)\}}. \quad (14)$$

Applying the normalisation rules defined in Eq. (8), the impedance and its R and C components can be expressed in a dimensionless form as follows:

$$Z^* = \frac{w}{2R_{e0}l}Z, \quad R^* = \frac{w}{2R_{e0}l}R, \quad C^* = \frac{t_{d0}}{\varepsilon lw}C. \quad (15)$$

Note that $R^* = 1$ and $C^* = 1$ correspond to two times the static resistance measured between two opposite ends of each undeformed electrode according to Ohm law, and the capacitance of the undeformed strip respectively. In case of undeformed strip ($\lambda_1 = 1$), the expression of the normalised impedance Z^* for a generic series resistance R_s^* is computed analytically as follows

$$Z^*(\omega^*) = R_s^* + \frac{1}{\sqrt{\frac{\omega^*}{2}}(1+j) \tanh\left(\sqrt{\frac{\omega^*}{2}}(1+j)\right)}. \quad (16)$$

The corresponding analytical expressions for Y^* , R^* , and C^* can be directly retrieved from (16) based on (12)-(15), thus are omitted for conciseness. In case of a generic $\lambda_1(x)$, one has to resort to numerical methods to integrate (9) and, in turn, compute the corresponding port quantities.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The model developed in Section 3 is here used to conduct numerical investigations, aimed at studying how different deformation patterns λ_1 , piezoresistive coefficients n , and lumped series resistance R_s^* affect the input port electric response of the membrane. All calculations are conducted in a dimensionless fashion, based on equations (9) and (12)-(15). Numerical integration of the boundary problem (9) is conducted in Matlab using fourth-order solver *bvp4c*, using analytical solution (10), and using complex-valued coefficients for the definition of the differential equation and boundary conditions.

4.1 Validation of the numerical model

As a first verification step, we verify consistency of the numerical integration problem by comparing it with the analytical solution provided by (16). In this case, we consider $\lambda_1 = 1$, $n = 0$, and $R_s^* = 0$. The two models are compared in terms of adimensionalized admittance Y^* , rather than the impedance Z^* , as the former is the quantity which one would typically measure in a voltage-controlled capacitive device. Both numerical and analytical admittance values are computed over a frequency range $\omega^* \in [0.1, 100]$, and plotted in Figure 2. The results confirm the consistency of the numerical method with the target analytical solution.

Figure 2. Simulation results in terms of admittance magnitude and phase as a function of the frequency for the undeformed configuration with $\lambda_1 = 1$, comparison between numerical and analytical models.

4.2 Effects of deformation pattern

The first set of simulations is conducted by considering how the input port behavior of the DE strip changes when imposing generic deformation patterns λ_1 . Deformation profiles of the following form are considered

$$\lambda_1(x^*) = 1 + \sum_{i=1}^m A_i \Psi_i(x^*), \quad (17)$$

where m is the number of perturbations, A_i is a perturbation scaling factor, and the normalized perturbation $\Psi_i(x^*)$ is a smooth bump function satisfying

$$\Psi_i(c_i) = 1, \quad \Psi_i(c_i - \delta) = \Psi_i(c_i + \delta) \quad \forall \delta > 0, \quad \Psi_i(x_i^*) = 0 \text{ if } x^* \leq c_i - 0.5s_i \vee x_i^* \geq c_i + 0.5s_i. \quad (18)$$

Parameters c_i and s_i denote the center and range of $\Psi_i(x^*)$, respectively, in such a way that $\Psi_i(x^*)$ is nonzero only in an interval of size s_i centered around c_i . An example of smooth function $\Psi_i(x_i^*)$ satisfying (18) is given by

$$\Psi_i(x_i^*) = \begin{cases} \exp\left(1 + \frac{1}{\left(\frac{x_i^* - c_i}{0.5s_i}\right)^2 - 1}\right) & \text{if } \left|\frac{x_i^* - c_i}{0.5s_i}\right| < 1, \\ 0 & \text{if } \left|\frac{x_i^* - c_i}{0.5s_i}\right| \geq 1, \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

which will be used in all subsequent simulations.

Four different scenarios are considered, all reported in the first column of Figure 3:

- Scenario 1 (first row of Figure 3): four different-single perturbation profiles ($m = 1$) are applied to the center of the strip and distributed through its entire length, each one with $c_1 = 0.5$ and $s_1 = 1$ but having different amplitudes A_1 ;
- Scenario 2 (second row of Figure 3): four different single-perturbation profiles ($m = 1$) are applied to different locations of the strip, each one with $s_i = 0.25$ and $A_i = 0.5$ but having different center points c_i ;
- Scenario 3 (third row of Figure 3): four different single-perturbation profiles ($m = 1$) are applied to the center of the strip, each one with $c_i = 0.5$ but having different combinations of s_i and A_i such that the former increases as the latter decreases, in such a way that the integral value of λ_1^2 is the same in all cases (thus ensuring the same static capacitance);
- Scenario 4 (fourth row of Figure 3): two different perturbation profiles are considered, the first being a single localized deformation ($m = 1$) applied to the center ($c_1 = 0.5$, $s_1 = 0.25$), and the second being the sum of two deformations ($m = 2$) applied to two different locations ($c_1 = 0.2$, $c_2 = 0.8$, $s_1 = s_2 = 0.25$). The amplitude is larger in the former case, but the static capacitance of the strip is the same in both cases.

Note that for Scenario 1 it is expected that the different profiles result in a different capacitive behavior in the low frequency regime, while for Scenarios 2-4 the amplitudes A_i are computed in such a way the capacitance C^* has the same low-frequency value when changing the deformation profile. This way, we can study if deformation profiles which result in a same static capacitance change can be discriminated by looking at higher frequency impedance data. For comparison purpose, an additional scenario corresponding to a completely undeformed membrane ($\lambda_1 = 1$) is added in each row of Figure 3, reported as a dotted black line.

Simulations are conducted for all profiles considering $n = 0$ and $R_s^* = 0$. For each case, results are reported both in terms of equivalent R^* and C^* (second column of Figure 3), as well as magnitude and angle of the normalized admittance Y^* (third column of Figure 3), considering a frequency range $\omega^* \in [0.1, 100]$. Analyzing the first row of Figure 3, it is observed how increasing the maximum deformation up to $\lambda_1 = 1.25$ makes both static capacitance and resistance larger up to 33% and 18%, respectively, while simultaneously increasing the admittance magnitude and reducing its cut-off frequency. Those results are consistent with the expected behavior

of DE sensors based on simple lumped impedance principles.⁷ The second row of Figure 3 reveals that applying the same deformation farther from the electrodes input port reduces the capacitance cut-off frequency of about $\Delta\omega^* = 1$, while the low-frequency capacitance value remains the same. A similar trend is observed in the admittance angle, while the resistance is reduced by 3% below the undeformed level for the closest deformation and then increases progressively with increasing disturbance application point up to 21% the undeformed level. This effect reveals that impedance measurements could be used to effectively detect the location of a deformation on the membrane, and confirm the experimental findings in earlier works.¹³ By inspecting the third row of Figure 3, the different deformation with different amplitude/spread combinations result in almost identical frequency responses for all electrical parameters under investigation. We can foresee that it might be hard to discriminate among those types of deformations solely based on input port measurements, at least for the case in which the electrodes sheet resistance is constant ($n = 0$). Finally, the fourth row of Figure 3 reveals that the number of load application points, given the same static capacitance, has a moderate change of 1 – 2% on the capacitance and a $\Delta\omega^* = 0.5$ on admittance phase shift behavior at intermediate frequencies, while there is a more meaningful scaling effect of about 10% on the resistance at low frequencies. This result seems to suggest that this information may be retrievable from input port electrical measurements, although the sensitivity of those measurements may be lower compared to the scenarios analyzed in the first two rows of Figure 3.

4.3 Effects of electrode piezoresistive properties

The simulation studies from Section 4.2 is repeated by considering different piezoresistive coefficients n . In particular, while in Section 4.2 we considered the simplest case of constant sheet resistance ($n = 0$), we will now consider three additional cases in which the sheet resistance increases proportionally to the square root of the stretch ($n = 0.5$), the stretch itself ($n = 1$, as suggested by Ohm law), and the square of the stretch ($n = 2$). Those parameter values are assumed to be prototypical, and are meant to represent possible piezoresistive behaviors encountered in electrode materials, see¹⁷ for instance. In all simulations shown in this section, $R_s^* = 0$ is considered.

The same simulation studies from Figure 3 are repeated for the new values of n , and the results are reported in Figure 4 for $n = 0.5$, in Figure 5 for $n = 1$, and in Figure 6 for $n = 2$, respectively. By comparing the figures, it can be seen that increasing n reduces the capacitance cut-off frequency while leaving the same low-frequency behavior. The resistance change, instead, increases accordingly while maintaining the same bandwidth. Specifically, while for $n = 0$ the largest deformation induces a resistance increase of about 18%, for $n = 2$ this increase exceeds 50%. In the admittance plot, the most visible effect is a larger spread of the phase shifts for the different profiles for a larger n . All such results are compatible with an overall increase in electrode resistance, as expected. By comparing the cases for the second rows, it can be seen that the sensitivity of the plot to the different deformation profiles is reduced for $n = 0.5$, with the plots becoming identical for $n = 1$. In effect, for $n = 1$ and $R_s = 0$, one can rewrite Eq. (9) by introducing coordinate change $d\xi = \lambda_1^2 dx^*$, leading to the following boundary value problem:

$$\begin{cases} j\omega^* V_\omega^*(x^*) = \frac{d^2 V_\omega^*}{d\xi^2} \\ V_\omega^*(0) = 1 \\ \frac{dV_\omega^*(1)}{d\xi} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

whose solution is independent of λ_1 . The resulting admittance for $\lambda_1(0) = 1$ then reads as:

$$Y^*(\omega) = \frac{I_\omega^*(0)}{V_\omega^*(0)} = -\frac{1}{\lambda_1^2(0)} \frac{dV_\omega^*(0)}{dx^*} = -\frac{dV_\omega^*(0)}{d\xi} \quad (21)$$

which is independent of $\lambda_1(x^*)$. Interestingly, for $n = 2$ the sensitivity of the electrical quantities to the deformation profile becomes even larger than for the $n = 0$ case, and the trends are reversed. Specifically, for $n = 0$ the deformation closed to the measurement port corresponds to the largest capacitance bandwidth, while for $n = 2$ the same deformation corresponds to the smallest capacitance bandwidth. The maximum change in

capacitance bandwidth and static resistance for $n = 2$ are of about 50% and $\Delta\omega^* = 1.5$, respectively, in contrast to 21% and $\Delta\omega^* = 1$ of the case with $n = 0$. A similar effect is also observed in the third and fourth rows of the figures, with the sensitivity of the plots to the deformation profiles decreasing progressively until $n = 1$ is met, and then increasing again but with an opposite trend. Interestingly, the third row of Figure 6 shows a non-incremental change of about 5% in both capacitance and resistance behavior for the different profiles, which could be potentially detected. Similar considerations hold true for the scenario in the fourth row, where for $n = 2$ we two profile result in a maximal changes in resistance and capacitance of about 6% and 2%, respectively. Those results seem to suggest that electrodes whose sheet resistance increases with a high power of the stretch might be favorable for implementing advanced distributed sensing patterns.

4.4 Effects of lumped series resistance

To conclude our simulation investigation, in this section we study how the lumped series resistance R_s^* affects the overall sensing properties. In real scenarios, this resistance can be interpreted as the parasitic resistance of the driving cables, the output resistance of the voltage source, or any similar parasitic effect. Therefore, it is meaningful to study how such unwanted effect would, at least in principle, affect the sensing accuracy.

In practice, we expect realistic values of R_s^* to be smaller than (or at least comparable to) the equivalent series resistance of the electrodes. For this reason, in all subsequent simulations, the selected values of R_s^* are always referred to the electrode quasi-static resistance in undeformed configuration \bar{R}^* . This quantity is computed by taking the low-frequency limit of the undeformed analytical impedance equation (16) with $R_s^* = 0$ and extracting the real part, i.e.,

$$\bar{R}^* = \lim_{\omega^* \rightarrow 0^+} \Re \left\{ \frac{1}{\sqrt{\frac{\omega^*}{2}}(1+j) \tanh\left(\sqrt{\frac{\omega^*}{2}}(1+j)\right)} \right\} = \frac{1}{3}. \quad (22)$$

It is interesting to note that $\bar{R}^* \neq 1$, meaning that the quasi-static value of the resistance inferred from impedance measurements is different from the resistance measured in between the two edges of the strip electrode.

To study the effect of the lumped series resistance on the overall port behavior, Figure 7 shows the admittance of the undeformed DE strip ($\lambda_1 = 1$) with $n = 0$, computed via (16) for progressively increasing values of \bar{R}^* given by $R_s^* \in \left\{0, \frac{1}{3}\bar{R}^*, \frac{2}{3}\bar{R}^*, \bar{R}^*, 2\bar{R}^*, 5\bar{R}^*\right\}$. The true strip admittance Y^* (continuous blue line in Figure 7) is compared with a simplified lumped admittance Y_l^* given by

$$Y_l^*(\omega^*) = \frac{1}{Z_l^*(\omega^*)}, \quad Z_l^*(\omega^*) = R_s^* + \bar{R}^* - \frac{j}{\omega^* \bar{C}^*}, \quad (23)$$

where \bar{R}^* is computed according to (24), while \bar{C}^* is given by

$$\bar{C}^* = \lim_{\omega^* \rightarrow 0^+} - \frac{1}{\omega^* \Im \left\{ \frac{1}{\sqrt{\frac{\omega^*}{2}}(1+j) \tanh\left(\sqrt{\frac{\omega^*}{2}}(1+j)\right)} \right\}} = 1. \quad (24)$$

The simplified lumped admittance Y_l^* approximates the overall strip frequency response with a lumped RC series where the respective constant capacitance \bar{C}^* and resistance $R_s^* + \bar{R}^*$ are given by the corresponding low-frequency limits of the capacitive and resistive parts of Y^* . The comparison between the continuous and lumped approaches to characterize the DE electrical admittance is motivated by the fact that the latter are far more adopted in the literature,^{7-9,18-20} and thus it is of interested to understand under which conditions lumped approaches become inaccurate. By inspecting Figure 7, is observed how the two admittances always coincide at low frequencies, and diverge as ω^* increases. The most notable difference is in the admittance asymptotic behavior for very large frequencies, as for $R_s^* = 0$ the true admittance Y^* converges to an angle of 45° and its magnitude becomes linearly increasing, while the simplified lumped admittance Y_l^* always converge to an

angle of 0° and to a constant magnitude (in agreement with classic frequency response theory for first order linear high-pass filter). As the value of R_s^* increases, the cut-off frequency of both admittance plots decreases as expected, while the angle and magnitude of Y^* are better approximated by the ones of Y_l^* at higher frequencies. For the highest of the tested values $R_s^* = 5\bar{R}^*$, Y^* and Y_l^* are almost indistinguishable. This result suggests that inspecting the measured frequency response of the admittance, and seeing how it compares with the behavior expected from a first order linear high-pass filter, could provide insights on the relative weight between electrodes and external resistances.

Further studies are then conducted by considering $n = 0$, and repeating the simulations from Section 4.2 considering 3 different values of R_s^* , i.e., $R_s^* = \frac{1}{3}\bar{R}^*$ shown in Figure 8, $R_s^* = \frac{2}{3}\bar{R}^*$ shown in Figure 9, and $R_s^* = \bar{R}^*$ shown in Figure 10. Higher values of R_s^* are not considered, as in typical practical scenarios we expect the lumped series resistance not to dominate the electrode intrinsic resistance. By comparing all the plots, it is observed how increasing R_s^* leaves the capacitive behavior unchanged, while the resistance is shifted upwards while keeping the same relative change, as expected. At the same time, as R_s^* increases the slope of the admittance is reduced while the maximum phase shift at $\omega^* = 100$ decreases to a minimum of about 10° . In case of the plot in the second row, the relative changes in the resistance amplitude are reduced from an original 21% of the case with $R_s^* = 0$ to an increase of 9% in the case $R_s^* = \bar{R}^*$. We conclude that care must be taken in designing the system in such a way that the external lumped resistance is as small as possible, as increasing its value has a negative impact on the sensitivity of the resulting sensing scheme.

Figure 3. Simulation results in terms of capacitance and resistance (center column) and admittance magnitude and phase (right-hand column) as a function of the frequency, considering a piezoresistive coefficient $n = 0$ and no additional series resistance such that $R_s^* = 0$. Each row corresponds to a different pattern of deformation profiles (left-hand column).

Figure 4. Simulation results in terms of capacitance and resistance (center column) and admittance magnitude and phase (right-hand column) as a function of the frequency, considering a piezoresistive coefficient $n = 0.5$ and no additional series resistance such that $R_s^* = 0$. Each row corresponds to a different pattern of deformation profiles (left-hand column).

Figure 5. Simulation results in terms of capacitance and resistance (center column) and admittance magnitude and phase (right-hand column) as a function of the frequency, considering a piezoresistive coefficient $n = 1$ and no additional series resistance such that $R_s^* = 0$. Each row corresponds to a different pattern of deformation profiles (left-hand column).

Figure 6. Simulation results in terms of capacitance and resistance (center column) and admittance magnitude and phase (right-hand column) as a function of the frequency, considering a piezoresistive coefficient $n = 2$ and no additional series resistance such that $R_s^* = 0$. Each row corresponds to a different pattern of deformation profiles (left-hand column).

Figure 7. Simulation results in terms of admittance magnitude and phase as a function of the frequency for the undeformed configuration with $\lambda_1 = 1$, the different plots compare the true admittance Y^* with the equivalent lumped one Y_l^* for different values of R_s^* .

Figure 8. Simulation results in terms of capacitance and resistance (center column) and admittance magnitude and phase (right-hand column) as a function of the frequency, considering a piezoresistive coefficient $n = 0$ and additional series resistance $R_s^* = \frac{1}{3}R^*$. Each row corresponds to a different pattern of deformation profiles (left-hand column).

Figure 9. Simulation results in terms of capacitance and resistance (center column) and admittance magnitude and phase (right-hand column) as a function of the frequency, considering a piezoresistive coefficient $n = 0$ and additional series resistance $R_s^* = \frac{2}{3}R^*$. Each row corresponds to a different pattern of deformation profiles (left-hand column).

Figure 10. Simulation results in terms of capacitance and resistance (center column) and admittance magnitude and phase (right-hand column) as a function of the frequency, considering a piezoresistive coefficient $n = 0$ and additional series resistance $R_s^* = \bar{R}^*$. Each row corresponds to a different pattern of deformation profiles (left-hand column).

5. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a model-based numerical investigation of distributed sensing capabilities of dielectric elastomer membrane. The goal of the study is to understand whether one can infer different deformation profiles present on the membrane, such as distributed loads with various intensities, solely based on the information available at a single electrical measurement port. Leveraging a distributed-parameter physical model, various numerical simulations were conducted by imposing different deformation profiles onto the membrane, and studying how those affect the frequency response behavior at the electrical measurement port. Equivalent resistance, capacitance, and admittance are used as metrics to evaluate the electrical performance. Based on the conducted simulations, it is deduced that changing individually the amplitude and the location of an applied deformation produces meaningful changes to the measurable electrical quantities, provided that the stretchable electrodes' stretch-deformation relationships follows a non-ohmic behaviour. Remarkably, this is true even if the different deformation patterns result in a same static capacitance, confirming the importance of multi-frequency data analysis in distributed DE sensing. On the other hand, measuring simultaneous changes in deformation amplitude/distribution that result in the same static capacitance appears as almost unfeasible, while inferring the number of contact point appears as potentially achievable, even though with limited sensitivity. Further simulation studies seem to suggest that the sensitivity of the information retrieval increases in the presence of electrodes whose sheet resistance has a higher-than-linear dependency on the stretch, and decreases the higher the lumped resistance connected in series to the DE membrane is.

Future studies will be targeted at experimentally validating the approach, and in using the model to optimize the pattern of (possibly bi-dimensional) electrodes to maximize sensitivity to a given DE sensor task. Data analysis techniques will also be studied to extract the deformation pattern from measurable input port quantities with the minimum number of information (e.g., number of frequency measurement points).

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